

Recovery of lintnerized starch from starch granules of eight rices differing in amylose content and final gelatinization temperature.

the alkali digestibility test on whole kernels of milled rice suggests that the whole kernel also reflects this starch property. To better understand the property, the characteristics of starch granules of eight rices differing in amylose content and gelatinization temperature were studied at IRRI. The rices were lintnerized or corroded in 2.2 N HCl at 35°C for 15 days. Lintnerization of rice starch granules consisted of a fast stage of 7 to 9 days involving the amorphous portion of the granules, and of a slower stage involving the crystalline portion. The weight recovery of lintnerized starch ranged from 6.6 to 21.1% and was greater for samples with higher gelatinization temperature (>70°C) and, to a lesser extent, high amylose content (see figure). Lintnerized starch had sharper X-ray diffraction peaks (more crystalline) than native starch. At the same amylose content, rice starch granules with high gelatinization temperature had a greater crystalline fraction than those with low gelatinization temperature.

The residual starch from both waxy and nonwaxy rices consisted mainly of two fractions with about 15 and 30 glucose units. The 15-glucose-unit fraction was linear and corresponded to the size of the outer chain length of rice amylopectin. The fraction consisting of 30 glucose units was probably a mixture of singly branched and linear dextrans, as indicated by the incomplete debranching into the 15-glucose-unit

fraction by pullulanase. Differences in mean molecular size of the lintnerized starch (19 to 30 glucose units) were due to differences in the ratio of those two fractions. Thus, differences in

gelatinization temperature of starch granules and their accessibility to various chemicals such as HCl and KOH were verified to be related to degree of crystallinity of the granules. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Occurrence of rice tungro virus in Tamil Nadu

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Rice tungro is caused by a virus that is known to be transmitted by leafhopper vectors. In recent years tungro has been epidemic or epiphytotic, often striking suddenly and devastating large areas of rice. The existence of tungro in India remained obscure until 1969, when a severe epidemic took a heavy toll of the rice crops in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar.

A tungro outbreak was noticed in this tract during kharif (July–Oct.) and pishanam (Nov.–Mar. 1977–78), seasons of 1977. The disease was observed in severe proportions in the southern districts of Tamil Nadu — Ramnathapuram, Madurai, Tirunelveli, and Kanyakumari. The disease incidence was severe in rice varieties ADT 31, TKM 8, TN1, IR8, IR5, ASD 11, Co 40, Co 25, and Bhavani — but IR20 was completely disease free. Ponni, Culture AS 3827, Culture AS 1391, and eight other entries — 1201, 1203, 1205, 1208, 1209, 1217, 1219, and 1230 — were found moderately resistant to tungro. ❧

A possible source of resistance to rice ragged stunt disease

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Preliminary results of a search for sources of resistance to rice ragged stunt disease reveal that the variety Ptb 21 Acc. no. 11053 received from the Central Rice Research Institute of India may be resistant; it consistently had a low percentage of seedling infection after ragged stunt inoculation by viruliferous

brown planthopper (BPH) *Maparvatu fugens* in screen cages and in a screenhouse.

The resistance of this Ptb 21 sample to BPH has not been determined, but another Ptb 21 sample Acc. no. 6113 received from the Andhra Pradesh Agricultural Research Institute in Hyderabad is known to be resistant to all three known BPH biotypes. Hence, Ptb 21 Acc. no. 11053 may also be resistant to BPH. Even so, the low percentage of seedlings of Ptb 21 Acc. no. 11053 infected with ragged

Infection of rice seedlings with ragged stunt disease after inoculation by two methods. IRRI, 1978.

Acc. no.	Variety	Seedlings infected with ragged stunt (%)		Brown planthopper resistance ^a
		Cage method	Screenhouse method	
105	TN1	92	96	S
7733	Gangala	71	84	R
6113	Ptb 21	—	—	R
11053	Ptb 21	3	12	—

^aAt IRRI Entomology Department. S = susceptible; R = resistant; — = data not available.